

The Role of Radio Lake Victoria in Enhancing Integration and Cohesion among Residents of Border Two Sub-location in Kisumu County, Kenya

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Abstract:- Majority of Kenyans listen to radio with 95% of the rural population having access to radio. Kenya has experienced violence almost after every General Election where thousands of people were killed and displaced from their homes. Radio stand accused yet studies have shown that radio can be used to promote peace and security at places like Border Two sub-location which recorded casualties in the 2007-08 Post-Election Violence. Radio Lake Victoria has had the highest rate of provocative speech broadcasted in Kenya. Investigative studies on the role of radio in promoting peace not only have methodological limitations and different motivational focuses, but also left out two main variables; clearness and correctness of radio programs in enhancing integration and cohesion. This study therefore sought to establish the role of Radio Lake Victoria in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. The study utilized systematic sampling to obtain 318 respondents from a population of 1542 while purposive sampling was used to select 10 respondents at the radio station where questionnaire and key informant interview guide were used respectively, in a cross-sectional study design. The study established that clearness of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhanced integration and cohesion with a mean of 3.866 and a standard deviation of 1.040, whereas correctness of the Radio Lake Victoria programs also enhanced integration and cohesion with a mean of 3.070 and a standard deviation of 1.066. The study concluded that clearness and correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs were relevant in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location and advocated for the implementation recommended to ensure a lasting peace. The study findings could be used by the media company in formulating policy that ensures integration and cohesion. Other researchers could also use the study as a secondary material to conduct more studies in relevant areas.

Keywords:- Media and Peace; Radio Lake Victoria; Cohesion and Integration; Political Conflict.

I. INTRODUCTION

Political violence according to Gotzsche-Astrup (2021) latches on discussed mechanisms and not only are such violence disruptive, they sometimes lead to mortalities and aggravated assaults against perceived enemies in the

political equation. Violence of whatever nature is antithetical to integration and cohesion and political violence arising from poor management of election dominates the hierarchy of violence everywhere. Community radio, as Dabrowski et.al (2021) pointed out, is a relevant tool in passing information to a given community that has perceived benefits and betterment of the community. Opinions differ as to whether community radio can reliably achieve sustainable cohesion and integration in the backdrop of cyclical elections in most democratic economies. There is no doubt however that community radio is a cheaper means of mass media whose ability to reach a particular community has not characterized intense debates in communication discourse (Dabrowski et.al, 2021)

Globally and especially in North American countries such as Mexico, Hayes (2017) avers that the level of awareness of the radio programs is made manifest by the extent of participation by local participants to whom the program is targeted. Radio programs such as radionovela which is a type of radio drama are aimed at enhancing not just local values, but also peaceful co-existence in a wider scheme of community interaction. According to Bilali and Vollhardt (2013) radio drama creates awareness in two basic ways. Firstly, the priming effect of the radio drama is laced with information that speaks to the most authentic selves of the audience and thereby passes information that is intended such as cohesion and integration. Secondly, there are radio call-ins after the acoustic performance that enables callers to express their satisfaction, appreciation or even dissatisfaction. Radio presenters then make clarifications that play to the awareness being created such as peace and stability.

According to a study conducted by Bello and Hadiza (2020) on the level of awareness and community radio, the researchers utilized simple random sampling to obtain 100 respondents to whom questionnaires were administered. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that community radio created awareness that was clear on national issues given the level of participation by the local community on the radio program. Although the study is credible, it utilized a small number of respondents that make generalization everywhere difficult. The study also focused on only one dimension leaving out other dimensions such as specific radio programs, timing of the radio programs, name of presenters of the programs as well as duration of the programs and how the dimensions

collectively signifies the level of awareness with reference to integration and cohesion. Therefore, the level of awareness and clarity of the local radio programs that enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location remains unknown.

In Kenya, according to Mweu (2019) has always been marred by violence around election and particularly after general elections and 2007-08 post-election violence was no exception. The bungled elections not only contributed to mistrust of the electoral management system in the country, it also led to loss of lives including the lives of children as well as bodily injuries of thousands of protesters and peaceful individuals who got entangled in the melee accidentally. Local community radio according to Maina (2016) is a credible instrument in the orchestra of integration and cohesion and in mitigating violence and preaching peaceful coexistence in the community if it is properly deployed. The effectiveness of radio in integration and cohesion is however a black and white phenomenon given the nuances such as ownership of the radio station, profits, political orientation and community targeted especially in a multicultural setting (Mweu, 2019).

According to a study on local radio and cohesion conducted by Kipoma (2014), the researcher utilized a case study design with a sample size of 100 respondents. The study employed questionnaires to collect primary data from the identified respondents. Descriptive statistics was then utilized to analyze data. The study revealed that the radio programs were effective and correct in enhancing integration and cohesion in the country. Although the study was viable, it only utilized questionnaires in data collection leaving out other tools such as focused group discussions and key informant interview guides to corroborate the questionnaire since the questionnaire may not give room for clarification and lead to misunderstanding. Additionally, the study focused on effectiveness but left out other key dimensions of effectiveness such as correctness, clearness and concreteness of the program messages. It therefore follows that the effectiveness of the radio programs that enhance integration and cohesion in regard to the named dimensions is still unknown.

A. Statement of the Problem

Radio Lake Victoria was named as the tribal radio with the highest rate in provocative framing of broadcast in the run up to 2007 general elections in Kenya. Similarly, despite the fact that radio can play a crucial role in de-escalating violence and tension within the local community, Border Two sub-location recorded 40% of the injuries sustained in the 2007-08 post-election violence within Nyando Sub-county. Although there were fatalities recorded from other Sub-locations, it recorded the highest number of injuries in Nyando Sub-county and Kisumu County in general. There are many studies that have sought to examine the role of community radio and peace-building initiatives. There is however, no study that has focused on the role of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in regard to two key variables namely, correctness of radio programs, as well as clearness of radio programs

and how such variables enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two Sub-location. The role of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two Sub-location in regard to the named variables is therefore unknown, hence the study.

B. Objectives of the study

The main study objective was to examine the effectiveness of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two Sub-location. However, the study was guided by the following specific objectives.

- To establish the clarity and effectiveness of Radio Lake Victoria program messages in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two Sub-location
- To examine the correctness and effectiveness of Radio Lake Victoria program messages in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two Sub-location

C. Significance of the Study

The study could be significant in a lot of ways. For instance, the study could be used by the Kenyan government for policy formulation. The government could use the study findings to formulate policies that could guide community radio programs regardless of their ownership, profit objectives and political orientation to produce programs that contribute to integration and cohesion especially during electioneering period. For practice, the study could be used not only by Radio Lake Victoria but also other community radios to implement the findings of the study not just to contribute to integration and cohesion, but also to get a bigger percentage of listenership from those who like peace building initiatives. Other researchers could also utilize the study as a secondary source of data in conducting other empirical studies in related disciplines.

D. Scope of the Study

The study was delimited to the title: the effectiveness of Radio Lake Victoria in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two Sub-location, thereby leaving out other sub-locations in Nyando Sub-county. Therefore, the findings was generalized in Border Two sub-location and recognized beyond the geographical scope of the study given that the findings of the study was valid and scientific in nature. The study was also delimited to two main variables namely, clarity as well as correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs messages and how they collectively enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two Sub-location.

E. Theoretical Model of the Study

The current study was guided by Agenda Setting Theory. Agenda setting theory demonstrates the power of legacy media to give the audience what to think instead of what they are actually thinking about. Through news items and programs the legacy media is able to engineer the thinking of the masses and shape such thinking to the predetermined propositions which makes the media such as radio very powerful in achieving integration and cohesion when used correctly (McCombs et.al, 2014).

According to Yeojin, Youngju, and Shuhua (2017), Agenda Setting Theory is based on two principles namely what to think about and framing. What to think about is the scenario where the media does not necessarily tell the audience what to think but what to think about given the news items or programs thereto. This happens because the dominant themes of the media will inform conversations in work places and informal arrangements where people debate and discuss the media content. On the other hand, framing is whereby the media influences the audience to follow a particular line of thought. In such a case, the media already have an end goal and their work is to use loaded language or particular terminology that will shape the thinking of the audience so as to come to a given conclusion predetermined by the media gatekeepers and owners.

In community radio programming the two tenets which are what to think about as well as framing play a big role in passing the message to the community. Given that Agenda Setting Theory makes the media such as radio to pervade the thing of the audience as McCombs et.al (2014) points out, this can increase the level of effectiveness, the structuring of the radio content to make it clear as well as improving the correctness of the radio programming so as to enhance integration and cohesion among the people targeted by such programs. On the other hand, given that the media such as the radio can use framing to direct the audience to come to a particular conclusion, the level of effectiveness, clarity as well as correctness of the radio programs can be made to lead to conclusions that enhance integration and cohesion in a given demography (Yeojin et.al (2017)

Although Agenda Setting Theory fits well with the current study, it has its limitations just like any other theory. According to Engl (2020) Agenda Setting Theory assumes that the audience has no ability to think on their own despite what the media presents which may not be the case all the time. Similarly, other listeners and viewers may lack the capacity to analyze the news item or the content of the program to come to the conclusion desired by the media gatekeepers. Agenda Setting Theory also ignores government regulations and policy frameworks under which the media operates. Such policies frameworks and government regulation may check the content of the media and deny it the great influence and power to pervade the thinking of the members of the society.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

It is a foregone conclusion that for a radio program to address integration and cohesion, the listeners must be aware of the clarity of the programs and community radios are no different. According to Hayes (2017) the knowledge of specific radio programs measures the level of awareness and clarity of a given radio program. Often the listeners would know the specific program by name and salient features of the program all of which constitutes awareness of the program and how clear it is to their issues. For instance Mexico radio listeners would easily acknowledge radionovela, a drama program that can be pervaded with messages that are targeted at the listeners, owing to its

clarity to address their issues. According to Dabrowski et.al (2021), such popular radio programs like melodrama can be infused with subtle messages about integration and cohesion, the ideal proposition of radio gatekeepers through agenda setting.

According to a study conducted by Rone (2020) which was aimed at establishing how awareness and clarity of radio programs contribute to peace building initiatives in Austria, the researcher employed literature survey design. The results were analyzed using inferential statistics and results were presented in Tables and charts. The findings indicated that the knowledge and clarity of the radio program had a significant correlation with peace building metanarratives. Although the study is credible, it was conducted in a developed country and not in a developing country like Kenya yet there are differences in technology and way of life between the two countries that cannot be ignored. The study also focused only on specific radio programs on peace building initiatives leaving out other dimensions within the framework of level of awareness and clarity on integration and cohesion.

Similarly, the knowledge of timing of the radio programs is also a manifest of awareness levels of the listeners about the radio programs and also a manifest of its clarity. According to Bergh (2021) the timing of a radio program is often primed to target a particular cohort. For instance, programs for adults in content are always aired after the watershed periods while programs for children are aired during the day or over the weekends when the children are at home, hence their clarity. Other programs are for the general family and are also aired during the day. It follows that knowledge of the timing of the radio program is a predictor of the levels of awareness and clearness of a radio program. According to Rone (2020), depending on who is targeted, a radio program can be laced with messages of integration and cohesion in the wider scheme of sustainable peace building especially in societies that are politically volatile and many other post war economies.

According to an empirical study conducted in Tanzania by Lwoga (2017), the aim of the study was to establish the knowledge of rural radio and how it addressed the plight of rural farmers. The study was qualitative in nature and selected 8 radio program operators to be the study sample. The results revealed that knowledge of timing of the program enhances the farmers' knowledge about farming activities and also makes it clear to them. As credible as this study may be, it utilized a small sample size which makes generalization in every context difficult. Additionally, the study had a different motivational focus, it only focused on farmers and the role of radio in enhancing farming activities leaving out knowledge of the specific radio program and how effective it can enhance integration and cohesion in the community.

Correctness as (Mweu, 2019) asserts, is the degree to which a radio programs addresses integration and cohesion successfully using messages which are complete so that the listeners do no struggle to make sense or ask many questions about the message of the radio in regard to peace and tranquility for the community. Completeness is a function of effective radio messaging so much so that the listener does not have to doubt the intention of communication or any other metanarratives about the message that would make the communication ambiguous.

According to a study conducted by Martin-Santana et.al (2015), the researchers intended to establish how the voice of the presenter correctly influenced the effectiveness of the messages. The study used four factor experimental design with 16 radio programs. The study also sampled 987 respondents for the study. The results revealed that completeness did not contribute to integration and cohesion. Although the study is dependable, it only focused on the voice of the presenter and how it influenced effectiveness and thereby leaving out completeness and correctness as a factor to influence integration and cohesion. The study also utilized experimental design yet experimental designs create artificial situations. Therefore, participants can easily be influenced by artificial situations and compromise the reliability of generalization.

Correctness of radio messages is another measure of program for its effectiveness in enhancing integration and cohesion among listeners. According to Kipoma (2014), correctness is the extent to which the radio presenters use proper grammar in communicating the messages to the masses. The use of language is broad and also involves the use of sayings, proverbs as well as other figures of speech as correctly as possible to avoid ambiguity and to pass the message of integration and cohesion in a manner that the targeted listeners understand clearly. Correct message is therefore clear enough to pass the message that needs to be passed to change the perceptions of those targeted and to achieve sustainable integration and cohesion. Correct message is accurate and therefore reduces ambiguity by using exact terminologies that can be easily understood by the audience. Therefore, if the message about integration and cohesion is correct and clear, it could enhance integration and cohesion provided that the radio station owner and the program directors work together on the same objective and are inclined towards peaceful coexistence.

A study done by Obasike (2016), the intention was to investigate the correctness in relation to effectiveness of community radio as a tool for community peaceful coexistence. The study was mainly qualitative in nature and the design was meta-analysis. The study established that community radio did not contribute to peaceful coexistence. Although the study is valid, it focused on the effectiveness of community radio on peaceful coexistence and not how correctness of community radio contributes to integration and cohesion. The study also used meta-analysis as a methodology yet there is no agreement among researchers as to the method of inclusion and exclusion in regard to meta-analysis design.

According to Mweu (2019), the correct message is vivid and tangible and is supported by facts and figures to eliminate misunderstanding to enhance credibility of the radio message. Therefore, if the facts and figures provided by the radio message differ considerably with the facts known to the audience, the message cannot be said to be concrete. On the other hand, if the facts given by the radio presenter supports the facts already in the public domain, the message is said to be concrete and correct, hence leading to no misunderstanding.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The study employed cross-sectional study design. According to Dillman (2000), the benefits of a cross-sectional study design in an empirical study is that it allows the study to be conducted in a specific point in time and not over a long period of time which therefore reduces abnormal variances. It also allows the researcher to compare many different variables at the same time. The current study was conducted at a specific point in time and not over a longer period of time in years. This therefore made the design suitable for the study.

B. Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Border Two sub-location, Nyando Sub-county in Kisumu County, Kenya. The people of the sub-location were mainly rural farmers and small traders. The sub-location borders the Rift-Valley to the east. In 2007-08, Border Two sub-location had the highest number of casualties as a result of Post-Election Violence in the sub-county, owing to the disputed 2007 presidential election results. Border Two Sub-location has been a hot spot area in every General Election cycle in Kenya with the 2007-08 Post Election Violence being the worst. In addition, no similar research has been carried out in this area on the effectiveness of radio programs in promoting integration and cohesion as vernacular radio stands accused as the main perpetrator of the Post-Election Violence in Kenya.

C. Target Population

The study targeted a population of 1542 adult members of the sub-location. The sample population were household heads who listen to Radio Lake Victoria. The population was justified because the researcher conducted the study that links Radio Lake Victoria to integration and cohesion of the local community and the population understood the language of the radio and the programs thereto.

D. Sample Design

The sample design described the sample size estimation method as well as the sampling technique that the study employed.

E. Sample Size Estimation Strategy

In order to get the right sample size, the study used Taro Yamane's statistical formula (Yamane, 1973) using a confidence level of 95% and margin of error being 0.05. The formula is as follows:

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$$

Where:

n=the required sample size

N=the entire population

e=is the error term (0.05)

Taking the total population to be 1542, the formula yields the following sample

$$n = 1542 / (1 + 1542(0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 1542 / (1 + 1542(0.0025))$$

$$n = 1542 / (1 + 3.855)$$

$$n = 1542 / 4.855$$

$$n = 317.6107$$

$$n = \mathbf{318}$$

The sample size was thus 328 because 10 respondents were obtained from Radio Lake Victoria for oral interview.

F. Sampling Technique

The study used systematic sampling technique. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), systematic sampling is more meaningful where the population is diverse and plural. In the current study the population was diverse and plural and consisted of individuals with different economic backgrounds and standing in the community. The researcher therefore divided the population with the sample size to get 5. Through randomization, the researcher then began from the 10th person in the study which when added to 5 is 15. The first person was therefore the 10th person, the second person was 10 plus 5 which was 15, the third person was 5 plus 15 which was 20 and the process went on until the number 318 was achieved. Purposive sampling was then used to obtain 10 respondents from the Radio Lake Victoria which consisted of program manager, production team, presenters and program controller.

G. Data Collection Procedure and Instruments

Before data collection ensued, the researcher got adequate approvals from Maseno University as well as approvals from the county government from the local area where the research was conducted. The researcher then visited the community for a formal introduction and to build rapport with the community's keepers. During such visits, the researcher also mapped areas and routes as well as directions that helped navigation of the area easier. Thereafter, the researcher went back for data collection.

The researcher used questionnaires and key informant interviews to collect primary data. Questionnaires was administered to the household heads while the key informant interviews were administered to the radio presenters, program controller, production team, and program manager. According to Yamane (1973), questionnaires are suitable in research because they are capable of collecting large amounts of data in a short period of time while key informant interview guides help in corroborating the questionnaire to mitigate the limitations of the questionnaire so as to end up with reliable generalization. The researcher acknowledged that using questionnaires and key informant interview guides (KIIG) were adequate to ensure reliable responses.

H. Reliability of Instrument

As Meller, (2001) pontificates, reliability of measurement concerns the degree to which a particular measuring procedure gives similar results over a number of repeated trials. Chronbach's Alpha test of internal consistency was used to test reliability. The coefficient level of clarity was 0.821, while the coefficient of correctness of the radio program was 0.801 which means that the instrument was reliable. Thus a cutoff point of more than 0.7 was tolerated which ensured reliability of the instrument.

I. Validity of the Instrument

Validity tests according to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) is the degree to which a test measures what it is supposed to measure and suggests truthfulness. To ensure validity, expert judgment was sought so as to ensure that the instruments are consistent with the intent of the study and that the framing of the questions are in order.

J. Data Analysis and Presentation

Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. It follows that mean and standard deviation were used to analyze quantitative data while thematic content analysis and narratives were used to analyze qualitative data that come from key informant interviews. Findings were then presented in Tables and in narrative forms.

K. Ethical Consideration

The study upheld ethical issues. Necessary approval was sought from the Maseno University permit committee together with the Ministry of Information and Communication Technology to allow data collection to be undertaken. Informed consent is also a principle underpinning empirical studies. As such, the researcher wrote a letter specifically to every participant. Similarly, the researcher ensured that every work used in the study was cited so as to eliminate instances of plagiarism. The researcher sought for the consent of the Sub-chief of Border Two sub-location in Nyando Sub-County before working in his area of jurisdiction. Additionally, the researcher ensured that no participant was forced or induced to participate in the study and could withdraw from the study whenever they wanted. The respondents were also assured of their confidentiality. The researcher informed the interviewees in good time and set a convenient date, time and place for the interviews.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Demographic of Study Respondents

The actual sample size was thus 328 respondents. However, 28 respondents could not be traced hence the study obtained responses from 300 respondents. It means that the response rate was 91% which was adequate enough to allow the study to continue. The rule of thumb is that a response rate of more than 70% is adequate enough to enable the study to proceed. The demographics of the respondents captured in the study included gender, age, level of education, employment status, as well as number of years spent in the sub-location.

Table 1 Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	160	53
Female	140	47
Total	300	100

Source: Research Data (2021)

According to Table 1, the results show that the majority of respondents (53%) were male while female respondents were 47% meaning that there was no huge variability between the genders of respondents. It therefore, means that the responses of the study could be relied upon to construe a credible generalization given that there was no bias in terms of gender of respondents. All the gender got the opportunity to participate.

In addition to gender categorization, the researcher sought to establish the age category of respondents so as to ensure credibility of responses. Table 2 demonstrates the findings of the study in terms of the age of respondents.

Table 2 Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	50	17
21-30	50	17
31-35	100	33
35 and Above	100	33
Total	300	100

Source: Research Data (2021)

According to Table 2, the majority of responses fell between the ages of 31 and 35 years old which had 33% as well as above 35 years old which also had a response of 33% in the same findings. Respondents who fell between the age of 18 and 20 years were 17% just like the respondents whose age bracket was between 21 and 30 years old. This therefore shows that over 80% of respondents were above 20 years old and were therefore able to contextualize the phenomenon under investigation and thus provide responses that were relied upon for empirical generalization.

Additionally, the study sought to establish the level of education of respondents. Table 3 shows the findings of the study in terms of the level of education of respondents.

Table 3 Level of Education

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
Primary	30	10
Secondary	150	50
Tertiary	70	23
University	50	17
Total	300	100

Source: Research Data (2021)

As per Table 3, the study findings show that the majority of respondents (50%) had secondary school level of education while only 10% of respondents had primary level of education. Further, 23% of respondents had a tertiary level of education. On the other hand, 17% of respondents had a university level of education. It concludes that all the respondents (100%) had formal education and were therefore able to read and understand the content of the questionnaire and thus provide responses that were relied upon to construe empirical generalization.

The study also sought to establish the employment status of the respondents. In particular, the study wanted to know whether the respondents were employed or not. As such, the study tested three levels of employment which are contractual employment, self-employment, as well as casual laborers. The results in Table 4 shows the findings of the study.

Table 4 Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Employed contractually	50	17
Self employed	150	50
Casual laborer	100	33
Total	300	100

Source: Research Data (2021)

Table 4 shows that the majority of respondents (50%) were self-employed while the minority (17%) were contractually employed. In addition, 33% of respondents reported that they were casual laborers. This therefore concludes that all the respondents (100%) had means of income generation and therefore did not need handouts to participate in the study. The researcher did not give any handouts, yet the respondents gave credible responses that ensured reliable generalization of findings.

On the number of years spent of the geographical scope of the study, Table 5 shows the results

Table 5 Number of Years Spent in the Area

Years in the area	Frequency	Percentage
0-1	30	10
2-5	50	17
6-10	70	23
Above 11	150	50
Total	300	100

Source: Research Data (2021)

According to Table 5, the findings show that the majority of respondents (50%) had lived in the geographical scope of the study for more than 10 years. This was followed by 23% of respondents who had lived in the area between 6 and 10 years. Only 10% of respondents had lived in the area for between 0 and 1 year which does not affect the outcome of the result while those who had lived in the area for between 2 and 5 years were only 17 % in the listing. This shows that all the respondents (100%) were residents in the area while 90% had lived in the area for more than two years during and before the elections. It therefore concludes that the respondents experienced the election period and were competent in providing responses that were then relied upon in constructing reliable generalization.

B. The Effectiveness of Radio Lake Victoria Programs in Enhancing Integration and Cohesion

The study sought to examine the effectiveness of Radio Lake Victoria in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. This sub-section addresses the specific objectives of the study. The first objective was to establish the clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. The second objective was to examine the correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs that enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location.

In regard to the first objective, the study tested a number of dimensions namely, knowledge of timing, knowledge of specific programs, participation in the radio programs, knowledge of the presenter as well as knowledge of the duration of the radio program concerning their clarity to the listenership. The study findings are shown in Table 6 below.

Table 6 Cleanness of Radio Lake Victoria Programs in Enhancing Cohesion and Integration

Statement for response	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
My knowledge of specific radio programs indicate the level of clarity of the radio programs that enhance integration and cohesion	300	1	5	3.98	1.112
My knowledge of timing of specific radio programs indicate the level of clarity of the radio programs that enhance integration and cohesion	300	1	5	3.42	1.921
My participation in the radio programs indicate the level of awareness and clarity of the radio programs that enhance integration and cohesion	300	1	5	4.01	1.012
The knowledge of the name of the presenter of the radio programs indicate the level of clarity of the radio programs that enhance integration and cohesion	300	1	5	3.81	0.614
My knowledge of the duration of the radio programs indicate my level of awareness and cleanness of the radio programs that enhance integration and cohesions	300	1	5	4.11	0.542
Overall mean and Standard deviation				3.866	1.040

Source: Research Data (2021)

According to Table 6, knowledge of the duration of the radio program as an indication of the level of cleanness and awareness had the highest significant factor of 4.11 representing the mean and 0.542 representing standard deviation. This was followed by participation in the radio programs as an indication of clarity of the radio program which had a significant factor of 4.01 representing the mean and 1.012 representing standard deviation. Knowledge of timing of specific radio programs as an indication of clarity of the radio program had the least significant factor of 3.42 representing the mean and 1.921 representing standard deviation. On the other hand, knowledge of specific radio programs as an indication of level of cleanness had a significant factor of 3.98 representing mean and 1.112 representing standard deviation. Finally, knowledge of the name of the presenter of the radio program as an indication

of level of clarity had a significant factor of 3.81 representing mean and 0.614 representing standard deviation. It can be deduced that the level of clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhances integration and cohesion given the overall means of 3.866. The small standard deviation of 1.040 shows that the responses were largely consistent.

The second objective was meant to ascertain the correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. The study tested a number of dimensions which are cleanness, completeness and concreteness of the radio program messages and whether such dimensions enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. Results of the findings were put in table 7 as shown below.

Table 7 Correctness of Radio Lake Victoria Programs in Enhancing Integration and Cohesion

Statement for response	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Completeness of radio program messages enhance integration and cohesion	300	1	5	2.01	0.901
Cleanness of radio program messages enhance integration and cohesion	300	1	5	2.91	1.425
Concreteness of radio program messages enhance integration and cohesion	300	1	5	4.29	0.872
Overall mean and Standard deviation				3.07	1.066

Source: Research Data (2021)

As per table 7, correctness of radio program messages in enhancing integration and cohesion had the highest significant factor of 4.29 representing mean and 0.872 representing standard deviation. On the other hand, completeness of radio program messages in enhancing integration and cohesion had the least significant factor of 2.01 representing mean and 0.901 representing standard deviation. Further, clearness of radio program messages in enhancing integration and cohesion had a significant factor of 2.91 representing the mean and 1.425 representing standard deviation. Given the average mean of 3.07, it can be deduced that effectiveness of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhances integration and cohesion. The small average standard deviation of 1.066 is an indication that the responses were consistent across the respondents.

C. Clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location

The study sought to establish the clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing cohesion and integration. The study established that clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhance cohesion and integration in Border Two sub-location given the mean of 3.866. The smaller standard deviation of 1.040 demonstrates that the responses were consistent and that there was no huge variability of responses from respondents. This therefore means that the residents of Border Two sub-location are not only aware of the clarity of the radio programs, but the radio programs are also ingrained in them to an extent that it enhances cohesion and integration among the residents. The responses were also consistent with the responses from key informant interviews. The major themes from key informant interviews were as follows: *“Through our programs, we broadcast messages targeted at peaceful coexistence.”* *“It is against the media council to instigate violence and as a responsible media we don’t instigate violence.”* *“The interaction between the presenters and the community helps in creating more awareness and clarity of our radio programs targeted at cohesion and integration.”*

The study findings were consistent with the findings of a study conducted by Rone (2020) in Australia who also established that awareness and clarity of radio programs contributed to peaceful coexistence. The study also supports Agenda Setting Theory. The theory posits that the media sets the agenda that is then followed by the listeners in the society. As such, the agenda set by Radio Lake Victoria in a clear manner contributes to cohesion and integration in Border Two sub-location.

D. Correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location

The last objective was aimed at establishing the correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. The findings of the study revealed that correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhances integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location given the mean of 3.07 in a 5 point likert scale. The small standard deviation of 1.066 indicates that there was low variability in terms of responses from the

respondents. It therefore means that the radio programs of Radio Lake Victoria are correct, effective and intentional in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. It therefore means that the degree to which radio programs attain the integration and cohesion in the community is not in doubt.

The findings were corroborated by the responses from the key informant interviews that were arranged thematically and put verbatim as follows: *“our presenters are well trained and they ensure that the messaging is correct and effective.”* *Our presenters ensure that the messaging is complete, clear and concrete.”* *The correctness and effectiveness of our messaging enhances integration and cohesion because it is delivered by professionals.”* The findings were, however, at variance with the findings of a study conducted by Rexa (2019) who established that correctness and effectiveness of radio programs did not enhance peaceful coexistence. The study findings also do not support Agenda Setting Theory. Such is because one of the limitations of Agenda Setting Theory is the belief that listeners have no capacity of their own to decide for themselves.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Summary of Study Findings

The first study question was, how does the clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location? The study established that the level of clarity of the Radio Lake Victoria programs enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. Specifically, clarity were enhanced by knowledge of specific radio programs, timing of specific radio programs, knowledge of the name of radio presenter as well as knowledge of the duration of the radio programs.

The second question was, how does the correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location? The study findings revealed that Radio Lake Victoria programs were correct and effective in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. In particular, the radio programs were complete, correct, clear as well as concrete.

B. Conclusions

The first objective of the study was to ascertain the clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. The study established that the clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhances integration and cohesion. The study concludes that clarity of Radio Lake Victoria programs are relevant for long term peaceful coexistence in the community.

The second objective was to examine the correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. The study established that the correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhanced integration and cohesion in Border Two

sub-location. The study concludes that Radio Lake Victoria program messages are correct and effective in enhancing integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location.

C. Recommendations of the Study

The key variables of the study were clearness of Radio Lake Victoria programs as well as correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs and how such variables may enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. Given the findings, it is clear that clearness and correctness of Radio Lake Victoria programs enhance integration and cohesion in Border Two sub-location. The study recommends that clearness and correctness of radio Lake Victoria programs should be enhanced so as to continue providing integration and cohesion in the long term.

D. Limitations of the Study

The study was limited to the sample size. The sample size that was used in the study is small compared to the population of a country like Kenya or even the global population. However, the researcher recognized that the study was empirical in nature and that a number of findings will have valid implications beyond the scope of the study area. Another limitation is found in the study design used. The study used cross-sectional study design yet the design does not assist to determine cause and effect and that the findings are only attributive. However, the researcher recognized that the design is scientific and has limitations just like any other design but does not compromise the reliability of generalization.

E. Area for Further Study

The study recommends that other researchers should conduct studies on the causes of Post-Election Violence in Kenya other than the media. The research should be conducted in other regions other than just Border Two sub-location in Kisumu County. It would be interesting to see how the findings compare.

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